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Istituto e Museo
di Storia della Scienza

Validated research assessment framework

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MUSEVAL - A Framework for Museum-Based Research Evaluation

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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the MUSEVAL framework for the evaluation of museum research activities, developed by Museo Galileo within the project funded by the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Programme.

MUSEVAL stems from the awareness that, although research is an integral part of museum practices, it often remains at the margins of traditional evaluation systems, which are primarily designed for the academic context. Museo Galileo, which structurally combines the functions of museum and research center and operates in a context where knowledge production, heritage care, and public communication are deeply intertwined, recognized the need for appropriate tools and criteria to make its research visible and assessable, as well as to guide its future development.

The document serves a dual purpose. On the one hand, it presents in a structured manner the principles, dimensions, and methodology of the MUSEVAL framework, conceived to evaluate research carried out in museums in a way that is consistent with the principles of research assessment reform promoted by the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA). On the other hand, it documents the conceptual and methodological process that led to its definition, grounding it in actual museum research practices and in the institutional context of Museo Galileo.

At present, the MUSEVAL framework is primarily focused on the evaluation of research activities and projects conducted within the museum. This choice responds to the need to make museum research visible and recognizable as an institutional practice, which is often overlooked in existing evaluation systems. It adopts a qualitative, contextual, and reflective approach, acknowledging the plurality of practices, outputs, and impacts of museum research, as well as its interdisciplinary, collaborative, and often infrastructural nature. In particular, the framework values both final outputs and intermediate results, work on sources, the production of tools and data, and research facilitation activities addressed to the scholarly community and to broader publics.

This document presents the conceptual foundations of the MUSEVAL framework. It provides a shared basis for understanding the evaluation of museum research and guiding future operational development. While it originates from the specific needs of Museo Galileo, the framework is designed to be adaptable to other museum contexts and to contribute more broadly to the international debate on the reform of research evaluation systems.

The document is complemented by annexes that serve a methodological and operational support function.

1. Introduction

1.1 Context: the reform of research assessment

The research evaluation systems currently adopted by national agencies, funding bodies, and research institutions present well-recognised shortcomings within the international scientific community. In particular, these systems rely predominantly on quantitative indicators and on a limited set of recognised outputs, mainly traditional scientific publications. This approach limits the ability to capture the actual quality of research, the plurality of scientific practices, and the diversity of institutional contexts in which research is carried out.

In recent years, these shortcomings have given rise to an international movement for the reform of research assessment, materialised in initiatives such as the [Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#), the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) — to which Museo Galileo is also a signatory — and the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment promoted by the [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#).

These initiatives converge around a set of key principles: the recognition of the diversity of research contributions, the centrality of qualitative and contextual evaluation, the abandonment of the inappropriate use of bibliometric metrics, and the alignment of evaluation systems with institutional missions.

1.2 Research in museums and evaluation challenges

The various definitions of museums adopted over time by the International Council of Museums (ICOM) explicitly recognise research as an integral and constitutive part of the museum mission. Despite this formal recognition, research conducted in museums often remains poorly visible and struggles to obtain adequate recognition within the broader landscape of scientific production.

Museums are frequently perceived as places that support the research of other actors — in particular universities and research centres — rather than as institutions capable of producing original research. In the case of university museums, this perception tends to relegate them primarily to the so-called “third mission”, overshadowing their contribution to the generation of new knowledge. Such a reductive representation does not reflect the actual complexity and depth of research activities carried out in museum contexts.

The difficulty in recognising and evaluating museum research is linked to a series of structural challenges that stem from its specific characteristics and that distinguish it from research as traditionally conceived in academia. A first critical issue concerns the often weakly formalised nature of research activities in museums. Unlike academic research, which typically results in publications in scientific journals, many investigative and study activities carried out in museums remain embedded in everyday practices or in objects and processes — such as exhibition development, the experimentation of conservation techniques, or the design of new educational approaches — that involve study, analysis, and knowledge production, but are rarely documented and communicated according to academic conventions and therefore seldom recognised as research “outputs”.

A further challenge concerns the variety of outputs and dissemination channels generated by museum research, as well as the attribution of impacts arising from these activities. Museum research often produces multiple types of outcomes, some directly linked to knowledge generation—such as exhibitions based on historical investigation, catalogues, instrument reconstructions, digital platforms, technical documentation—while others, such as educational programs or outreach activities, may derive from the research without constituting research themselves. Distinguishing between these cases is essential: for example, a didactic activity can represent research if it investigates innovative educational methods or learning processes, whereas its routine implementation primarily supports dissemination.

Each of these output types requires specific evaluation criteria capable of taking into account their purposes, target audiences, and modes of use. The effects of museum research tend to emerge in the medium to long term and in a diffuse manner, often extending beyond the boundaries of the scholarly community. An exhibition may influence public perceptions of a scientific topic; an educational programme may shape the learning choices of thousands of students; a historical reconstruction may stimulate new lines of academic research. These are significant impacts, yet they are difficult to measure in the short term and to attribute unequivocally to individual research activities.

This complexity is compounded by the intrinsically collaborative and interdisciplinary nature of museum research. Contributions are distributed across professional profiles—historians, conservators, IT specialists, educators—making the attribution of results and recognition of individual contributions challenging when using evaluation models focused on single researchers. Traditional quantitative metrics, designed for academic publications, are therefore inadequate for capturing the full value of museum research, as they tend to emphasize individual outputs over integrated and collaborative efforts.

By acknowledging the diversity of outputs and dissemination channels, the context of their production, and the collaborative processes involved, evaluation frameworks can better account for the specificities of museum research, recognizing both the generation of knowledge and the broader institutional and societal impacts that may emerge over time.

The challenges described above are fully shared by Museo Galileo and are partly intensified by its institutional positioning, which places it under the dual supervision of the Ministry of Universities and Research and the Ministry of Culture. This positioning makes Museo Galileo a particularly suitable context for developing reflections on research assessment that can coherently articulate the scientific and cultural dimensions of the museum mission.

The opportunity to concretely develop this reflection was provided by the cascade funding call promoted by CoARA, aimed at supporting organisations engaged in addressing the challenges of research assessment reform. Within this framework, Museo Galileo submitted a proposal under the “Institutional Change Projects” strand, with the objective of accelerating processes of transformation of internal evaluation practices and procedures through the development, testing, and implementation of criteria and evaluation tools tailored to the specific characteristics of museum research.

2. Objectives for Building an Evaluation Framework

2.1 Scope of the Evaluation

The MUSEVAL framework is designed to evaluate research activities and their outcomes, understood as processes, outputs, and intermediate results that contribute to the scientific, cultural, and educational mission of Museo Galileo.

The scope of evaluation includes:

- **research activities**, understood as project-based, methodological, and organisational processes spanning the full lifecycle of projects;
- **research outputs**, including final outputs (publications, exhibitions, digital tools, cataloguing resources), intermediate results (prototypes, draft versions, progressive releases of data and tools), and research infrastructure.

In its current configuration, the framework is not designed as a tool for evaluating individual researchers, nor as an automatic mechanism for individual assessment or career progression. Rather, it is intended to make the processes and outcomes of museum research visible and assessable as a collective and institutional practice.

This approach reflects the specificity of museum research, which unfolds through multidisciplinary and collaborative practices, involving diverse skills and professional roles. In this context, the value of research emerges from the interaction of different knowledges, roles, and contributions, as well as from the ability of projects to generate knowledge, tools, and impacts over time. Focusing on activities and outputs allows the collective, interdisciplinary, and distributed nature of museum research to be recognized, in line with the principles promoted by the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

2.2 Purpose of the Framework

While the starting point for the MUSEVAL framework is the specific needs of Museo Galileo, the exercise is placed within a broader perspective and is intended to provide useful insights for other museums, both nationally and internationally. In this sense, the project contributes to the ongoing discussion on the reform of research assessment systems, enriching it with an institutional perspective that is often overlooked: museums as knowledge-producing institutions.

For Museo Galileo, having explicit criteria and procedures for research evaluation primarily means **guiding future activities more consciously**. The museum conducts research across diverse fields — from history of science to cataloguing, from digital research to education and public engagement — producing heterogeneous outputs ranging from monographs to exhibitions, from digital platforms to instrument restorations. Without a structured reference framework, it is difficult to make strategic investment decisions, establish priorities, allocate resources, or assess outcomes in a continuous improvement perspective.

The MUSEVAL framework provides criteria and tools to support these decisions, while making the link between research activities and the museum's institutional mission more

visible and communicable. The evaluation criteria can also support the **promotion and valorisation of research activities**, helping to build an evidence-based narrative of impact. This narrative can be used to strengthen dialogue with other research actors, support the development of collaborations, and increase the museum's capacity to participate successfully in competitive research projects.

For other museums, Museo Galileo's experience can serve as a **starting point adaptable to different institutional contexts**. The development of the evaluation framework involves consultation with other museums, fostering a dialogue that allows not only refining the proposal but also identifying common challenges and needs. This process contributes to building a shared vision and a platform for discussion that can represent museums in communications with relevant Ministries and funding bodies. In the medium to long term, the framework can also support the recognition of museums conducting research as **independent research institutions**, following models adopted in other international contexts, such as the United Kingdom.

Finally, the MUSEVAL project contributes to the broader reflection on the transformation of research assessment promoted by CoARA. Museums represent a particularly significant case in this reflection, as they highlight the limitations of evaluation systems built primarily around academic publications. Museum research emphasises dimensions that traditional systems struggle to recognise: interdisciplinary collaboration between historians, technicians, conservators, and communicators; educational and cultural impact on audiences; the ability to translate specialised knowledge into accessible experiences. Developing appropriate criteria to evaluate these aspects is not only relevant for museums, but can also provide guidance for other areas of research where **social impact and public engagement** play a central role, particularly within the humanities.

3. Methodology for Developing the Framework

The development of the MUSEVAL framework is based on a **participatory and iterative methodology**, designed to ground the evaluation framework in the actual practices of museum research and to avoid adopting abstract models or approaches derived solely from the academic context. The process was structured into **five main, complementary phases**.

The **first phase** involved a series of interviews with Museo Galileo staff (Andrea Bernardoni, Sara Bonechi, Filippo Camerota, Gaia Cugini, Giovanni Di Pasquale, Natacha Fabbri, Roberto Ferrari, Alessandra Lenzi, Maddalena Napolitani, Maurizio Sanesi, Valentina Vignieri), aimed at understanding how research is actually conducted within the institution: which activities are perceived as research, what specific characteristics and constraints shape their execution, and what types of outputs they generate. The interviews included a variety of professional roles within the museum — historians of science, librarians, curators, cataloguers, technicians, and IT specialists — covering different career stages and levels of responsibility, reflecting the inherently collaborative and interdisciplinary nature of museum research. In addition to the interviews, a questionnaire was administered to collect further perspectives and reflections, which were subsequently analysed and integrated into the qualitative material gathered.

In **parallel**, a comparative analysis of international research evaluation models and practices was conducted to contextualise the reflection and avoid building the framework entirely from scratch. The study examined different types of museum institutions — libraries, ethnographic

museums, natural history museums, and museums of the history of science — enabling the identification of approaches and tools relevant to the context of Museo Galileo, such as the use of project forms, exhibition presentation methods, and forms of result validation in scientific and professional domains (see Annex 1 for details).

The **third phase** consisted of two internal workshops for discussion and co-design, aimed at translating the information collected in previous phases into a structured proposal. These workshops enabled the definition of the **guiding principles** of the evaluation framework, the identification of evaluation dimensions, quality criteria, and types of empirical evidence that could be used.

The **fourth phase** involved consulting a group of representatives from Italian museums and cultural institutions, selected to reflect the diversity of the national museum landscape in terms of thematic fields, institutional configurations, and the critical mass dedicated to research. The participants included university museums (Museo Giovanni Poleni, Padua), natural history museums (MUSE, Trento), archaeological museums (Museo Egizio, Turin), art museums (Uffizi Gallery, Florence), and science and technology museums (Museo Astronomico e Copernicano, Rome; Museo Leonardiano, Vinci). This consultation confirmed the existence of **shared challenges**, such as the recognition of museum research and the difficulty of evaluating non-traditional outputs, while also highlighting the need for a **flexible framework** capable of adapting to different contexts and avoiding rigid solutions.

Following this external consultation, a **fifth phase** of internal feedback and validation was conducted, involving researchers and museum staff engaged in research activities. The aim of this phase was to assess the clarity, relevance, and applicability of the framework in relation to daily practices, collecting critical observations, suggestions for improvement, and requests for clarification. This process contributed to **strengthening the distinction between activity evaluation and individual assessment**, clarifying the temporal dimension of evaluation (ex-ante, in progress, ex-post), and consolidating the framework's role as a tool for self-assessment and strategic support.

The insights gathered during this internal feedback phase were integrated into the **framework**, which represents a shared synthesis of institutional needs, research practices, and orientations emerging from dialogue with the broader museum community.

4. Results

4.1 Research at Museo Galileo: Scope, Fields, and Specificities

A key outcome of the development of the MUSEVAL framework has been the shared definition of the scope of activities recognised as “research” within Museo Galileo. As outlined in previous sections, these activities are integral to the institution’s mission and develop along two complementary dimensions:

- **knowledge production** (scientific content);
- **the study, design, and development of tools, practices, and infrastructures** that make such knowledge accessible, usable, and reusable.

Museo Galileo’s research activities can be grouped into **six highly interconnected domains**.

1. **Historical and historiographical research:** This domain encompasses in-depth study of scientific instruments, manuscripts, and ancient texts, as well as the historical and cultural contexts in which science developed. The work is based on analysis of primary sources, reconstruction of technical innovation processes, and investigation of the relationships between science, technology, and society across different periods.
2. **Cataloguing, documentation, and collection conservation:** This includes material analysis of objects (materials, construction techniques, state of preservation), reconstruction of their historical trajectories, and preventive conservation. This domain also supports external research by assisting scholars consulting collections and documentation, generating new knowledge about the objects and informing conservation and interpretative practices.
3. **Research applied to digital tools and infrastructures:** Museo Galileo develops platforms, databases, and digital services that go beyond simple digitisation, requiring data modelling, adoption of interoperability standards, and experimentation with innovative methodologies to represent and link complex information. The design and management of digital infrastructures are considered full-fledged research activities.
4. **Research on the museum experience:** This domain analyses how visitors interact with spaces, collections, and exhibits. Using qualitative and quantitative methods — behavioural observation, feedback collection, visitor data analysis, and, in some cases, measurements of emotional and cognitive responses — it produces knowledge that helps improve the Museum’s communicative effectiveness and accessibility.
5. **Public history:** Understood as research practice that engages the history of science with issues of public and contemporary relevance. This domain goes beyond disseminating established knowledge, producing original interpretations aimed at dialogue with society, involving both specialist and non-specialist audiences.
6. **Education, mediation, and outreach:** Considered spaces for experimentation and critical analysis of communication practices. Research in this domain focuses on methodological innovation, and adapting communication strategies to heterogeneous audiences.

4.2 Outputs, Intermediate Results, and Research Infrastructures

Research at Museo Galileo produces a wide variety of outputs, grouped into **four main categories**:

1. **Traditional scientific outputs:** Articles in journals, contributions to edited volumes, monographs, curatorial work, conference presentations, and specialised training activities (courses, seminars, schools). These outputs enable engagement with the scholarly community and situate museum research within academic circuits.
2. **Museum and public history outputs:** Temporary and permanent exhibitions (with catalogues), urban projects, interdisciplinary initiatives, outreach videos, educational tools, and public activities. These outputs translate research into multi-layered experiences accessible to diverse audiences.
3. **Collection-related outputs:** Cataloguing records — in the case of Museo Galileo *PST - Patrimonio scientifico e tecnologico* of the Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione (ICCD) — conservation studies, material analyses, and reconstructions of original instrument functions. These activities generate new knowledge about the objects and can revise or update established interpretations.

4. **Digital and infrastructural outputs:** Web platforms, digital editions, repositories, datasets, data models, and applications. These tools not only disseminate research results but also enable further research by other scholars, positioning the Museum as a research infrastructure.

In addition to final outputs, the framework recognises the value of **intermediate results** (prototypes, beta versions, progressive releases of data and tools), which facilitate knowledge circulation and reduce the risk of retaining resources until a presumed state of “final completeness.”

4.3 Distinctive Features of Museo Galileo’s Research

Analysis shows that Museo Galileo’s research differs from traditional academic research in several structural ways:

- **Centrality of material heritage:** Continuous, direct engagement with objects guides research questions and grounds interpretations in material evidence.
- **Inherently collaborative and interdisciplinary nature:** Research integrates historical, technical, conservation, IT, and library expertise.
- **Multiple audiences:** This requires continuous translation and adaptation of results and shapes how research is conceived and communicated.
- **The Museum as facilitator and research infrastructure:** Through digital resources and reusable tools, a significant portion of activities lies in the fields of digital humanities and methodological innovation.

4.4 Evaluation Dimensions

Taking into account the type of activity, operational methods, and intended purposes — as revealed through the participatory process described above — the framework proposes **eight evaluation dimensions**, guiding the selection and implementation of research activities.

1. **Scientific and methodological quality:** Rigour in conducting research — accuracy in analysing historical sources, solidity of interpretations, and appropriateness of methods relative to the questions posed. For example, evaluating research on an ancient scientific instrument involves assessing the precision of documentary source examination, correctness of material analysis, and consistency of conclusions with available evidence.
2. **Museum value and contribution to the institutional mission:** Measures how research contributes to enhancing the Museum’s collections and supporting its scientific, educational, and cultural goals. A project may be scientifically sound but of limited relevance to the Museum’s mission. This dimension considers, for instance, whether research improves understanding of collection objects, produces content for exhibitions or educational activities, or strengthens the Museum’s positioning as a reference institution.
3. **Innovation and interdisciplinarity:** Assesses originality in content and methods, and the integration of knowledge from diverse fields. An innovative project might investigate a well-studied topic using new methodologies or perspectives.

Interdisciplinarity is crucial for achieving this, enabling perspective integration, new methodologies, and emergent research questions.

4. **Output production and diversity:** Evaluates the diversity and complementarity of research outputs relative to existing work, including both traditional products (catalogues, publications, reconstructions) and innovative formats (digital platforms, interactive exhibitions, educational videos), with attention to dissemination to specific audiences and support for STEM/STEAM learning.
5. **Communication quality and accessibility:** Considers how clearly and effectively research results are communicated, ensuring accessibility to diverse audiences through varied formats (texts, multimedia, interactive activities) and supporting inclusivity for different skills, language abilities, and cognitive needs.
6. **Technical quality and digital sustainability:** Applies specifically to digital outputs, evaluating interoperability, technical robustness, interface usability, and long-term sustainability. A digital platform may be innovative and content-rich, but if built with outdated technologies, lacking standards, or requiring constant maintenance without dedicated resources, it risks becoming unusable.
7. **Collaborations and networks:** Collaborations are both a means to achieve ambitious research and an outcome in themselves, strengthening relational capital and institutional visibility. This dimension assesses the ability of research to foster new relationships or consolidate existing ones with institutions, experts, and scholarly communities.
8. **Impact:** Can be scientific (influencing subsequent studies), educational (contributing to student and public learning), institutional (enhancing reputation and positioning), or social (affecting public perception of science or cultural heritage valorisation). Measuring impact is complex because effects often occur in the medium to long term and cannot be fully attributed to individual initiatives; yet this dimension is essential to capture the overall value of museum research.

The framework recognises that **not all research projects engage all dimensions**, but the absence of a dimension must be **explicitly considered and justified**, clarifying why it is not relevant given the project's objectives and characteristics. This ensures transparent and methodologically consistent evaluation.

4.5 Temporality of Evaluation

The MUSEVAL framework supports **distributed evaluation over time**, consistent with the processual nature of museum research and CoARA principles. Evaluation is not conceived as a one-off or solely retrospective act but as an **accompanying device** applicable at different stages of the research project lifecycle.

This section describes the **purpose and use of evaluation across temporal stages**. Operational methods (indicators, evidence, procedural steps) are defined in Section 4.6.

4.5.1 Ex-ante Evaluation

Ex-ante evaluation is intended to support the informed design of research activities and to verify their alignment with the institutional mission of the Museum. At this stage, the evaluation is not selective or punitive, but rather guiding and strategic in nature.

Specifically, ex-ante evaluation allows for:

- Clarifying project objectives and alignment with scientific and institutional priorities;
- Identifying relevant framework dimensions and justifying the non-applicability of others;
- Specifying expected outputs, distinguishing between intermediate results and final outputs;
- Making trade-offs between source work, infrastructure development, and product delivery transparent;
- Supporting informed resource allocation decisions.

From this perspective, ex-ante evaluation helps to legitimise differentiated project strategies, preventing the absence of certain outputs in the early stages from being interpreted as a deficiency.

4.5.2 In-progress Evaluation

In-progress evaluation is primarily **formative and supportive**, enabling monitoring of project development, valuing intermediate results, and guiding operational adjustments.

During this stage, evaluation focuses on:

- Recognising the value of source work, even without immediate visible outputs;
- Valuing prototypes, beta versions, and progressive releases of data and tools;
- Supporting decisions on the optimal timing for making resources and results public;
- Encouraging reflection and dialogue among researchers, management, and support structures

In-progress evaluation **does not produce final judgments** but strengthens research quality and reduces the risk of relevant activities remaining invisible or unrecognised.

4.5.3 Ex-post Evaluation

Ex-post evaluation provides a **comprehensive review of completed research activities**, serving organisational learning, accountability, and institutional communication.

This evaluation allows for:

- Analysing outputs produced and intermediate results achieved;
- Reflecting on observable impacts, acknowledging that they may manifest in the medium to long term and may not be fully predictable;
- Assessing the effectiveness of strategies relative to initial objectives;
- Building an institutional narrative grounded in qualitative and contextual evidence.

Ex-post evaluation does not automatically link outcomes to individual consequences but informs strategic decisions, future priorities, and the valorisation strategies of the Museum's research.

4.5.4 Coherence Across Evaluation Phases

The three temporal stages are **interconnected**. Choices and justifications developed during the ex-ante phase provide reference points for in-progress and ex-post evaluation. Similarly, ex-post results inform the design and evaluation practices of future projects.

In this way, MUSEVAL promotes coherent, transparent, and improvement-oriented evaluation, where temporality is a structural element rather than an external constraint.

4.6 Indicators and Evidence for Evaluation

For each dimension, the MUSEVAL framework identifies **observable indicators and documentable evidence** that can be used to support the evaluation of research activities.

These indicators do not constitute an exhaustive checklist or a set of standardized metrics, but rather a **flexible toolbox** to be selected and adapted according to the nature, objectives, and stage of the project (ex-ante, in-progress, ex-post).

The following table presents the **dimension–indicator matrix**, which serves as an operational reference for evidence collection and the construction of a qualitative evaluation.

Dimension	Observable Indicators / Evidence
1. Scientific and Methodological Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Completeness and accuracy of analyses • Consistency of methods and interpretations • Presence of verified bibliographies and sources • Cross-checks and technical verifications • Explicit documentation of methodological choices
2. Museum Value and Contribution to the Mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contributions to the enhancement of the Museum’s heritage (exhibitions, standardised catalogue records e.g. PST, conservation studies) • Use in educational and mediation activities • Alignment of the project with the Museum’s strategic objectives • Improvement of access to and understanding of relevant topics
3. Innovation and Interdisciplinarity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Originality of interpretative or methodological approaches • Experimentation with unconventional tools, practices, or formats • Documented interdisciplinary collaborations • Initiation or consolidation of new research lines • Integration of diverse professional skills
4. Production and Variety of Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diverse and complementary outputs (scientific, museum, digital, cataloging) • Consistency between outputs and project objectives • Added value relative to the state of the art • Formal and content quality of outputs • Presence of intermediate results (prototypes, beta versions, progressive releases)
5. Communicative Quality and Accessibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarity and appropriateness of language for target audiences • Production of informative, educational, or mediation materials • Qualitative and quantitative feedback from users, visitors, or scholars • Accessibility of content (physical, digital, linguistic, cognitive)

Dimension	Observable Indicators / Evidence
6. Technical Quality and Digital Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adoption of standards and interoperability with other systems • Usability of platforms and tools (testing, analytics, feedback) • Availability of technical documentation, data models, and metadata • Sustainability over time (maintenance, updates, dedicated resources) • Consistency between data, objects, and adopted digital models
7. Collaborations and Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborations with universities, museums, archives, DH networks • Co-curation, joint projects, shared events • Feedback or endorsements from external partners • Participation in international or disciplinary networks
8. Scientific, Educational, Institutional, and Social Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reuse of results in subsequent research, theses, or projects • Use of content in educational and training contexts • Increased use and consultation of physical or digital resources • Observable changes in museum, conservation, or mediation practices • Active public engagement and participation • Initiation of new collaborations or follow-up initiatives

Indicators can be applied differently across ex-ante, in-progress, and ex-post phases, prioritizing project coherence and methodological quality in the initial stages, and focusing on output variety, facilitation of research, and observable impacts in subsequent stages.

Dimension	Ex-ante (Planning)	In-Progress (Development)	Ex-Post (Analysis and Learning)
1. Scientific and Methodological Quality	Coherence between objectives, sources, and declared methods; explicit methodological choices	Progressive accuracy of analyses; cross-checks and justified methodological adjustments	Overall consistency between method, analysis, and interpretations; robustness of conclusions
2. Museum Value and Contribution to the Mission	Alignment of the project with the Museum's mission and strategic priorities	Emerging usability of results in exhibition, educational, or mediation contexts	Actual contribution to heritage enhancement and institutional positioning
3. Innovation and Interdisciplinarity	Originality of project design; planned integration of diverse expertise	Activated interdisciplinary collaborations; experimentation with innovative practices or tools	Opening or consolidation of new research lines; recognizability of innovative value

4. Production and Variety of Outputs	Clarity regarding expected outputs; distinction between intermediate results and final outputs	Presence and quality of intermediate results (prototypes, beta versions, progressive releases)	Diversity, quality, and added value of produced outputs
5. Communicative Quality and Accessibility	Identification of target audiences; coherent communication choices	Progressive production of mediation materials; qualitative feedback	Clarity of language and actual accessibility of content
6. Technical Quality and Digital Sustainability	Motivated technological choices; adoption of standards and data models	Usability of tools; availability of technical documentation and metadata	Effective interoperability; sustainability over time and potential for reuse
7. Collaborations and Networks	Planned collaborations and their strategic relevance	Activated collaborations; joint projects or activities	Consolidation of networks; feedback and recognition from external partners
8. Scientific, Educational, Institutional, and Social Impact	Declared potential impacts (without predictive expectation)	Preliminary signals of use, interest, or reuse	Reuse of results; observable changes; new initiatives generated

4.7 Proposed Evaluation Methodology

The MUSEVAL framework proposes a general evaluation methodology consistent with the principles promoted by CoARA. It is based on a combination of objectifiable evidence (**quantitative**) and **qualitative, narrative assessment**, and is oriented toward a contextual reading of research activities. The methodology defines the **operational modalities of evaluation**—namely, how evaluation is conducted.

The methodology is articulated into **three main, complementary steps**, which can be applied—using differentiated approaches—across the ex-ante, in-progress, and ex-post phases.

The first step consists of **collecting indicators and evidence**. For each dimension of the framework, relevant indicators are selected in relation to the nature, objectives, and specific characteristics of the project. Supporting evidence may take different forms, including catalog records (PST, in the case of Museo Galileo), technical documentation, bibliographic references, peer-review processes (formal or informal), digital products, outreach and dissemination materials, data on resource use, collaboration agreements, or statements from external partners. The outcome of this phase is a **reasoned selection of relevant indicators**, accompanied by the evidence documenting their application.

The second step involves a **qualitative and narrative evaluation**. The collected indicators are interpreted through an argumentative text for each activated dimension, explicitly outlining strengths, critical issues, and the project choices made. Where one or more dimensions are not applicable, **their non-applicability must be explicitly stated and justified**, becoming an integral part of the evaluation. This step makes it possible to reconstruct the context of decision-making and to avoid a purely descriptive or additive reading of the evidence.

The third step is the preparation of a **project summary sheet**, which consolidates in a structured form the information collected and interpreted in the previous phases. The summary provides an overall view of the research activity and is conceived as a support tool both for strategic decision-making and for institutional communication.

Across all these steps, the methodology assigns a **formative function** to evaluation. Evaluation accompanies the development of research activities, fosters reflexivity, and makes explicit the trade-offs between work on sources, infrastructure development, and the release of outputs.

In particular, the framework promotes strategies for the **progressive release of data and tools**, recognizing the value of preparatory and infrastructural work even in the absence of final products or immediately observable impacts.

The MUSEVAL framework presented in this document represents a **first structured, yet still preliminary, version**, which requires further development before it can become fully operational and integrated into the ordinary processes of the Museo Galileo.

Conclusions

This deliverable has laid the conceptual and methodological foundations of the MUSEVAL framework, situating museum research within the broader international debate on research assessment reform and articulating its specific characteristics, challenges, and value. Building on an analysis of existing evaluation models and on the particularities of research practices in museum contexts, the document has defined a shared conceptual framework, a set of evaluation dimensions and indicators, and a coherent methodological approach aligned with the principles promoted by CoARA.

By foregrounding qualitative, contextual, and narrative forms of assessment, and by recognising the diversity of research outputs, temporalities, and impacts, MUSEVAL aims to provide a flexible and proportionate framework capable of capturing the richness of museum-based research while remaining compatible with institutional evaluation needs.

The work presented here represents a first, structured step towards the development of an operational evaluation model. The next phase of the project will focus on translating this conceptual framework into practice through pilot applications, methodological refinement, and the progressive definition of operational tools and procedures, enabling the transition from a shared evaluative vision to its concrete and sustainable implementation.

Annex: International Benchmarking

Within the framework of the MUSEVAL project, a comparative study was conducted to understand how other international museums perceive, evaluate, and select their research activities. This benchmarking exercise made it possible to identify established practices, shared challenges, and examples of approaches that may inform the development of the Museo Galileo evaluation framework.

The analysis focused on institutions with different characteristics but all engaged in significant research activities: natural history museums, ethnographic museums, science and medical museums, and research libraries.

1. International museums analysed

The analysis involved five European institutions, representative of different museum typologies:

- Natural History Museum of Crete – University of Crete (Greece)
- Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (Austria)
- Musée d’Ethnographie de Genève (Switzerland)
- Rijksmuseum Boerhaave (The Netherlands)
- British Library (United Kingdom)

2. Cross-cutting conclusions

The comparative analysis highlighted several recurring elements in the research and evaluation practices of the institutions examined:

- 1. Predominance of traditional academic outputs**
Most institutions consider “classical” outputs as the primary products of research: scientific articles, conference participation, monographs, and doctoral supervision or training.
- 2. Primarily academic objectives**
The objectives set for research activities remain predominantly academic in nature: number of publications in peer-reviewed journals, participation in conferences, acquisition of research funding, and involvement in competitive research projects.
- 3. Delegation to peer-review mechanisms**
Strategies for evaluating and recognising research quality are often delegated to peer-review mechanisms and to formal or informal validation by the scientific community.
- 4. Informal approaches to research prioritisation**
At the planning stage, the selection and prioritisation of research projects are often based on informal or weakly structured mechanisms. However, there are significant exceptions, as described in the case study below.

3. Case study: The British Library

The British Library represents a particularly interesting case due to three distinctive elements:

- Its institutional recognition as an *Independent Research Organisation (IRO)*
- The existence of an explicit research strategy with dedicated governance
- Careful institutional communication regarding research activities and their impacts

3.1 Independent Research Organisation

A distinctive feature of the British Library is its recognition as an *Independent Research Organisation (IRO)* by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), a status it has held since 2006. This recognition enables the institution to compete for national research funding on a comparable basis with universities, opening significant opportunities for ambitious research projects.

To obtain and maintain this recognition, an institution must demonstrate:

- **High-quality research capacity:** at least ten researchers holding a PhD (or equivalent experience), and a staff track record including the coordination or co-leadership of innovative research projects over the past five years, including supervision of postdoctoral researchers and students.
- **Adequate financial support:** average support for research activities of at least £500,000 per year over the previous three years, demonstrating the availability of essential infrastructure and the long-term sustainability of research activities.
- **Relevance to Research Councils:** the significance and relevance of the institution's research capacity to the scientific themes of at least one of the seven UKRI Research Councils.
- **Impact experience:** proven ability to maximise the impact and value of research for the benefit of the economy and society.

IRO status represents a higher level of recognition for research activities, brings additional financial resources, and signals the institution's standing within the academic community.

3.2 Research Strategy and Governance

The British Library has published a dedicated Research Strategy for the period 2024–2030, which is embedded within the broader institutional strategy *Knowledge Matters 2023–2030*. The strategy defines the general principles guiding research, clarifies how the institution will use its expertise and collections to generate new knowledge, and supports decision-making regarding resource allocation and the identification of funding opportunities.

Strategic Objectives

The strategy articulates five objectives:

- **Building staff research capacity:** strengthening the research skills of existing staff and training the next generation of researchers through doctoral programmes, while facilitating continued engagement in integrated research initiatives.
- **Developing an inclusive research culture:** ensuring that staff at different levels possess research competences and can apply them when appropriate opportunities arise, supporting innovative practice-based research methods and reflective practices for library professionals.
- **Increasing research impact:** enhancing the visibility of research activities and effectively disseminating results (see section on *Communication of Research Impacts*).
- **Developing collaborative opportunities:** continuing to lead and participate in competitive research projects, creating cross-cutting research opportunities, strengthening existing partnerships and developing new ones, in alignment with the institution's strategy.
- **Maintaining IRO status:** reviewing and strengthening research processes and standards to sustain the quality and integrity of research activities and to comply with funder requirements.

Priority Research Themes

The British Library has identified four cross-cutting and multidisciplinary priority research themes:

- **Collection histories:** research on the history of collections to enhance understanding of how to manage and present them as custodian of the national memory. This includes provenance research, studies on the lives and legacies of collectors and institutions, and histories of curation, conservation, and dispersal.
- **New narratives:** the collections contain stories relevant to contemporary issues and with the potential to engage new audiences, which need to be brought to light through high-quality research. These projects inform many aspects of long-term public programming, including exhibitions, events, broadcasts, digital resources, and publications.
- **Innovations in library services:** libraries are research infrastructures and, as the national library, the institution must continue to adapt and improve the way it provides cross-disciplinary national infrastructure and services, responding to evolving needs and opportunities.
- **Policy and practice:** practice-based research addressing cultural and heritage policy and practice, sustainability, access issues, equality, diversity and inclusion in libraries, co-collecting and co-curation, learning programmes, information literacy, engagement with the creative industries, and the social, cultural, and economic value of libraries.

Governance

Research governance is structured through a **Research Strategy Group**, an internal body responsible for strategic oversight, advice, and guidance on the library's research priorities and activities. A subcommittee manages research ethics approval processes. The Group acts as the reference and monitoring body to ensure that research activities are conducted in accordance with the standards required of an IRO under UKRI regulations.

The **Research Development Team** supports the development of the institution's research profile, funding capacity, governance, and research capability through engagement with staff and with the external research community.

3.3 Research Support Mechanisms

The British Library has developed several instruments to support research activities:

- **Collaborative Doctoral Partnerships**, funded by UKRI through the Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC), enable joint doctoral supervision between the British Library and UK universities, aligned with the Library's thematic and institutional priorities.
- The **PhD Placement Scheme** offers doctoral students from all disciplines the opportunity to develop and apply transferable skills outside the university sector. Projects range from cataloguing and conservation to interpretation, policy research, resource development, and community engagement.
- **Scholar Fellowships**, including programmes such as the Chevening British Library Fellowships, aimed at mid-career professionals wishing to develop through work with the Library's collections and resources, and the National Trust and British Library Doctoral Fellowships, which provide professional development opportunities for current doctoral students.
- **Doctoral Open Days**, annual events designed to introduce doctoral students to the use of the Library's collections and resources.
- **Participation in competitive research projects**: the British Library is actively involved in projects funded by AHRC, ESRC, European programmes, and international foundations. In 2022–23, the institution was involved in 54 research projects, including 23 funded by various UKRI councils, 6 European projects, and 8 projects funded by international bodies.

3.4 Communication of Research Impacts

The British Library devotes particular attention to the institutional communication of its research activities, publishing an annual Research Report documenting completed projects, established collaborations, and achieved results. The 2022–23 report highlights involvement in 54 research projects, supervision of 25 collaborative doctoral projects with partner universities across the United Kingdom, organisation of training events involving 646 doctoral students, and numerous international collaborations.

This systematic reporting approach represents an element of particular interest for the MUSEVAL framework. The production of annual research reports not only enhances the visibility of activities carried out, but also contributes to building a coherent and documented impact narrative. A structured evaluation framework can support this process by providing guidance on identifying relevant dimensions to monitor and the evidence to collect, thereby facilitating the communication of results to both internal and external stakeholders.

4. Case study: Musée d'Ethnographie de Genève

The MEG is a public institution of the City of Geneva, founded in 1901. It holds a collection of over 75,000 objects of diverse nature (archaeology, religious artefacts, everyday objects, contemporary art, crafts) and more than 300,000 documents (books, photographs, iconographic documents, sound and music recordings) relating to approximately 1,500 cultures, both historical and contemporary, across five continents. The museum also houses a unique collection of musical recordings, the *Archives internationales de musique populaire* (AIMP), comprising more than 20,000 hours of music.

In 2017, it received the prestigious European Museum of the Year Award (EMYA) for the quality and originality of its cultural offer. In 2023, it became the first museum in Switzerland to obtain the THQSE label (*Très Haute Qualité Sociétale-Sociale-Sanitaire et Environnementale*) at gold level, certifying its commitment to sustainability and social responsibility.

Three elements make the Musée d'Ethnographie de Genève (MEG) a particularly relevant case study:

- An explicit strategic plan integrating research into the museum's overall mission
- An innovative conception of research outputs, including exhibitions, performances, and cultural collaborations
- A structured approach to the ex-ante and ex-post evaluation of activities

4.1 The 2020–2024 Strategic Plan

The MEG developed a strategic plan addressing four major challenges faced by ethnographic museums: the risk of obsolescence of the traditional “ethnographic museum” model in light of decolonial critiques; changing audience expectations and motivations; digital transition; and the need for transformation in internal professional culture. In response, the MEG defined a clear mission: to question received ideas, practices, and cultural representations in order to facilitate decolonisation and orient perspectives towards the future.

Based on this mission, the plan defines five strategic objectives:

- **Decolonising the museum:** giving voice to the heirs of those who were colonised, to creators and communities of non-dominant cultures; becoming a museum trusted by the communities of origin of its collections; promoting access to collections and archives; facilitating dialogue on restitution; establishing an international reputation in critical museology.
- **Strengthening the role as platform and partner:** collaborating regularly with individuals and institutions from other disciplines; building sustained links with institutions in other cities and countries; prioritising partnerships across all aspects of museum work, allocating one third of the operational budget to support equitable exchanges.
- **Diversifying and including new audiences:** developing audiences from cultural minorities and low-income populations; increasing repeat visits; increasing international visitors; exceeding 200,000 annual visitors.
- **Inspiring creative processes:** reinforcing an interdisciplinary approach that fosters exchanges between sciences, arts, and cultures; expanding opportunities for

creators to use museum resources; giving a greater role to music and sound in infrastructures and productions.

- **Becoming a benchmark institution for sustainable development:** integrating data-driven decision-making; promoting innovation and workplace well-being; contributing to sustainable development goals by minimising waste and pollutants; incorporating sustainability themes into all projects.

In line with its decolonising mission and the search for a “new relational ethics” with communities of origin, the MEG has defined five research axes guiding its scientific activities:

- **Critically examining the historical provenance of collections:** deepening knowledge of object provenance, particularly acquisition motivations and modalities, to ensure greater transparency of inventories, including informing source communities about sensitive objects held in collections.
- **Adopting new theoretical approaches:** developing new perspectives on the status of objects and sound archives, moving beyond Eurocentric views to value multiple perspectives and decolonise museum language.
- **Reconnecting collections with source communities:** restoring links between source communities across five continents and the collections or archives concerning them, with the aim of heritage reappropriation, co-constructing new knowledge and interpretations.
- **Inspiring creation by hosting artists:** fostering exchanges with creators to generate new artistic productions, encouraging researchers, culture bearers, and audiences to envision and co-create a decolonial future.
- **Supporting advanced research with external partners:** developing collaborations with universities, research centres, and other museums at local and international levels for joint research projects.

4.2 Innovative Conception of Research Outputs

A distinctive feature of the MEG is its recognition that **exhibitions, performances, events, and cultural collaborations** constitute full-fledged research outputs, on par with traditional academic publications. This perspective significantly broadens the range of recognised research outputs. Curators are encouraged to present their work in conferences and publications, while prioritising the original cultural production rather than focusing solely on theoretical contribution.

This approach is exemplified by the MEG’s participation in the *Initiative Bénin Suisse*, a provenance research project concerning collections from the Kingdom of Benin (Nigeria) held in Swiss museums. Funded by the Federal Office of Culture and coordinated by the Museum Rietberg, the project brings together eight Swiss public museums to determine which objects were looted during the British expedition of 1897 and through which stages the art market brought them to Switzerland.

The research identified nine objects originating from the Kingdom of Benin in the MEG collections. For some objects—such as a large ivory tusk bearing burn marks and a copper alloy belt mask published in a 1900 sales catalogue—provenance research demonstrated that they were part of the loot taken from the royal palace in 1897.

Alongside documentary research, the MEG co-produced *Le Miroir d'Iyagbon*, a theatrical performance created by Compagnie Onyrikon and Nigerian sculptor Samson Ogiamien. The performance engages with the provenance of African collections and denounces their status as “museumified” objects disconnected from their ritual uses.

The ambulatory performance begins in the Africa section of the MEG’s permanent exhibition, around a mysterious mask created by Ogiamien with the royal casters of Benin City. The audience is invited to follow this bronze mask in a procession through the streets of Geneva from the museum to a secret location where a sacred ritual takes place. This example illustrates how provenance research can result not only in scholarly publications but also in artistic productions that engage source communities and reach diverse audiences.

4.3 Evaluation of Research Activities and Projects

The MEG has developed an “agile” methodology for the ex-ante evaluation of research projects and cultural activities (i.e. a procedure to verify alignment with institutional objectives and potentially prioritise competing projects). Evaluation is based on a project sheet describing objectives, dissemination strategy, and methodology. Projects are assessed according to six criteria:

- **Alignment with the museum’s strategy:** joint assessment by management and cultural mediation to ensure coherence with institutional vision, mission, and strategic objectives.
- **Relevance of the dissemination strategy:** analysis of target audiences, communication tools, and capacity to reach priority audience categories.
- **Co-construction:** level of internal (multidisciplinary team) and external (stakeholders, source communities, partners) involvement.
- **Interdisciplinarity:** integration of multiple disciplines and methodological approaches.
- **Sustainability:** contribution to sustainable development goals and minimisation of environmental impact.
- **Social responsibility:** contribution to inclusion, audience diversification, and the development of a new relational ethics with source communities.

More recently, the MEG has initiated the development of an ex-post evaluation process for activities and their impacts. Through this approach, evaluation seeks to analyse:

- The positioning of activities in relation to the expectations of different stakeholders.
- The elements stakeholders identify as most important and meaningful when engaging with museum productions and staff.
- The correspondence between the elements identified as important by stakeholders and those defined by the museum.

Concretely, this effort aims to design an analytical “reading grid” composed of questions and areas of analysis enabling the museum to engage in dialogue with external stakeholders and monitor results across these dimensions. The strategic plan also foresees the establishment of an advisory committee tasked with assessing the success of implemented actions, with annual reports on progress achieved in relation to each objective.

5. How the results informed the MUSEVAL framework

The analysis of international case studies provides several insights for the development of the Museo Galileo evaluation framework:

- **Formal institutional recognition:** the UK IRO model highlights the importance of seeking institutional acknowledgements that legitimise the museum's research capacity.
- **Explicit research strategy:** both cases demonstrate the value of a formalised research strategy, with defined objectives, priority axes, and dedicated governance.
- **Broadening of research outputs:** as illustrated by MEG's approach, it is both possible and desirable to consider exhibitions, events, and cultural productions as legitimate research outputs.
- **Multidimensional evaluation criteria:** MEG's criteria (strategic alignment, co-construction, interdisciplinarity, sustainability, social responsibility) provide a model for assessment that goes beyond bibliometric metrics.
- **Stakeholder engagement:** MEG's ex-post "reading grid" suggests the importance of involving stakeholders in defining and measuring research impact.
- **Structured collaborations:** the British Library's programs (Collaborative Doctoral Awards, fellowships) demonstrate how to formalise collaborations with the academic world.
- **Systematic communication:** the British Library's practice of publishing annual research reports underlines the importance of regularly documenting and communicating activities and impacts.

These elements have been integrated into the proposed MUSEVAL framework and its eight evaluation dimensions, contributing to a vision of museum research that recognises both traditional scientific excellence and the specific forms of production and impact characteristic of cultural institutions.